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See also:

Usage workflows for ontology design pattern templates

Quick links:

- <https://github.com/INCATools/dosdp-tools>
- https://github.com/cmungall/owl_patternizer
- https://github.com/INCATools/dead_simple_owl_design_patterns/

Intro

Templated design pattern systems like DOSDP¹ and ROBOT² afford a variety of usage patterns. They can indeed be used purely for generative purposes, with whole branches of the ontology (or even the whole ontology) constructed from minimal TSVs (the extremes here are occupied by ontologies like OBA³ and ECTO). But they can also be used to document existing patterns, and to probe the ontology for sections that conform. A wide variety of intermediate states are possible, with edits happening in a mixture of TSV and OWL. But there is actually no need to do any generation, having a documented specification of your ontology's implicit structures is incredibly useful, and having this be a computable specification that can be used to probe the ontology is a powerful tool for quality control.

We have discussed these a lot but need to write down the general usage patterns in an easier to understand way. This is an initial stab. It should evolve into something less formal but it's good to start with a precise document from which we can derive something more editors friendly.

Related docs: [owl_patternizer draft](#)

This document focuses on DOSDP templates for simplicity and concreteness, but can be generalized to robot templates. Where we say “YAML” this refers to the template specification which should read as “TSV header” for robot. Note that robot doesn’t yet have a “parse” command (i.e. reverse the generate function) but this could easily be added.

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Basics

The key workflow tools here are dosdp-tools⁴ and robot. These provide the primitive operations that can be composed together in a variety of workflows. The key editing tools are Protege and a TSV editor of choice. A key OWL construct is owl:imports, which allows importing of axioms (including auto-derived axioms).

A newer approach is LinkML-OWL which treats DPs as metaclasses and TSVs as instance data, affording more flexibility, DP-level rules, consistency checking etc.

dosdp-tools generate

TSV + YAML ⇒ OWL

Note variations along a spectrum. A minimal setup may only generate labels and logical definitions. A more maximal one may auto-generate synonyms and text definitions and include slots for multiple manual annotation properties in the TSV.

dosdp-tools query

OWL + YAML ⇒ TSV

robot merge

OWL + OWL ⇒ OWL

Usage workflows

I enumerate a number of usage workflows here. Note that some ontologies may mix and match these within a single ontology, according to branch or module. In some cases, an actual usage pattern may straddle what is documented here.

There is no right or wrong workflow to use. This will depend on the ontology, and for particular branches of the ontology. It may vary throughout the history of the ontology.

In some cases, there are clear anti-patterns. If your ontology is entirely composed of fairly dumb repetitive compositional combinatorial classes then it is inefficient to manually edit this in Protege. Protege is not optimized for repetitive form-filling type editing.

Conversely, if you are constructing high-level classes such as the top level terms in GO or an ontology like obo-core then it probably doesn't make sense to have your source be TSVs and generate from these. This is because you are editing outside an IDE and do not have the benefits of integrated reasoning, seeing hierarchical context, structurally inferred properties etc.

In most cases, there will be some kind of mix with pros and cons. Many ontologies contain subsections that are partially combinatorial, but not all ontologies are compositional in nature. It's an **anti-pattern** to try and axiomatize everything.

The only true anti-pattern is never to formalize your patterns at all. There is no ontology where it doesn't make sense to at least use DOSDPs or similar mechanisms as a *documentative usage pattern*.

We distinguish essentially four major template workflows:

1. Ontology Seeding
2. Purely TSV-driven Ontology Curation
3. Skeleton Generation
4. Documentation
5. Augmentation
6. Gap filling
7. Autosuggestion of patterns and logical definitions
8. Integrated template and direct editing

Workflow 1: Ontology Seeding

The goal here is to use a templating mechanism to seed an ontology with a bunch of classes; after this, all editing is done in Protege.

Workflow:

1. Author TSVs/sheets and YAML
2. Run dosdp generate
3. Integrate individual components (robot merge, owl:imports)
4. Git add and commit OWL
5. Edit OWL in Protege (reasoner on)
6. Release using standard mechanism (e.g. make/odk running robot)
7. Discard original TSV (perhaps retain for provenance)
8. Continued maintenance: go to 4

With this approach, the original TSVs are discarded or archived. The YAML may also be discarded (call this "true seeding"). Or the YAML may be maintained, occasionally tweaked, and used for querying, in which case this becomes more of a **probe** usage pattern.

A variant of this approach is to execute the above workflow iteratively for different branches of the ontology, or to work with an existing ontology and to occasionally seed new branches or even mini sub-branches. Or seed new classes that fit into an existing set of classes

Strengths: The workflow is appealing in many ways. It allows rapid generation of arbitrarily large chunks of compositional classes. It is easier to source input from a wider variety of people as many people can edit TSVs without training. It also doesn't constrain editors as they can arbitrarily tweak afterwards; but this comes at a cost...

Weaknesses: This suffers many of the weaknesses of not using patterns at all. Subsequent tweaking of the ontology may diverge from patterns leading to non maintainability. This can be remedied by not following the “true seeding” workflow, but by transitioning from a seed workflow to another such as probe.

Examples: Many ontologies implicitly used a true seeding approach at least at some point in their history. Examples include EFO⁵. I suspect many parts of the FMA have been seeded by ad-hoc scripts (but note there was not even retention of logical definitions). Parts of the GO were definitely scripted in perl. Examples of ontology that have done this using dosdp includes FBbt (DPO)⁶

Workflow 2: Purely TSV-driven Ontology Curation

This is the extreme end of a spectrum, where an entire ontology or ontology branch is generated from TSV. Here, the editor **never touches the OWL for this branch in Protege or any other tool**. The OWL is still visible through imports of the generated axioms. (a variant of this pattern is “Skeleton” which allows adornment through Protege). All edits are in the TSV.

In some instantiations of this workflow, the TSV is minimalist, all it does is assign an ID to a composition, with autogeneration of everything else. With other instantiations, the editors expends more care on the TSV, occasionally over-riding the rdfs:label, text definition, or supplying their own additional annotation assertions. The key thing is that all edits are in the TSV.

An even more extreme advanced approach here is to autogenerate some parts of the TSV, e.g. to auto-gap fille, e.g. using Most Recent Common Ancestors (MRCAs). See patternizer paper for details.

Validation problem:

- Manual review of hierarchies are hard
- Potential: re-iterate hierarchies of some external ontology (MRE/ECTO)
- How do we document the design patterns (beyond templates) on a larger scale
 - absence as an example
- Right now: test cases lacking
 - inheres in x shold always be in a subclass of IIPO etc
 - Could be in yaml?
 - Formalise unit testing

Workflow:

1. Expert ontologist authors YAML
2. Ontology developer authors TSV

3. TSV is continually edited
4. ODK generates OWL from TSV
5. Editors view edit.owl which imports generated OWL
 - a. Edit axioms outside generated branches (if any)
 - b. View axioms in generated branches
6. Release merges generated OWL with edit.owl
7. Continued maintenance: go to 2 or 4 as appropriate

Strengths:

- Editing TSVs is easy for many. People can make drive-by PRs in GitHub. Or people can edit in Excel
- Frees up ontology editors from worrying about often-dumb repetitive compositional stuff and focusing on other branches
- Editors do not edit logical definitions in Protege (a frequent source of errors leading to lack of internal logical consistency and unintended logical consequences)

Weaknesses:

- While editing the TSV, cannot see things in a complete context
- Confusing/frustrating not be able to edit generated branches while in Protege
- Can lead to over-use; making things “fit into a pattern” when not appropriate (but IMHO this happens more when actually editing in Protege - see previous versions of HPO)
- Greater care must be dedicated to the generation and maintenance of IDs, especially if multiple patterns can apply to the same term, a term moves from one pattern to another or, even more difficult, pre-existing compositions are mapped from an external source (like ZP), and the composition has to be mapped to a previously generated term.

Examples: OBA, ECTO, XPO, ZP, PLANP

Workflow 3: Skeleton Generation

This is related to pure TSV driven, but the idea is to autogenerate a skeleton which can be adorned in Protege. Crucially, the adornment is **additive only**. This means that if we decide the text definition is in the domain of the TSV for a particular workflow, then that is where edits have to be made.

Workflow

1. Expert ontologist authors YAML
2. Ontology developer authors TSV. This typically has col1 = ID for class already in the ontology
3. TSV is continually edited
4. ODK generates OWL from TSV
5. Editors view edit.owl which imports generated OWL

- a. Edit axioms with complete freedom outside generated branches (if any)
 - b. View or adorn classes in generated branches, but no deletion of generated axioms
6. Release merges generated OWL with edit.owl
 7. Continued maintenance: go to 2 or 4 as appropriate
 8. Sub-workflows
 - a. Branch-wise management

Strengths:

- As per pure TSV-driven
- Allows editors to adorn classes in generated branches

Weaknesses:

- Division of source can be confusing
- Editors may try to delete axioms that are generated from TSV. These will reappear like zombies
- Makefile can be harder to set up

Examples:

- uPheno (EQ only)
- MAXO (variant of Skeleton: for example, you want to generate logical axioms for a particular, branch with many similar classes according to a design pattern)
- ENVO

Workflow 4: Documentation and Validation

This workflow is the most “traditional” in that no edits happen on TSVs (but note that this usage pattern can be bootstrapped from seeding), edits are done on OWL in Protege as usual. The crucial difference between these and “old school pre-pattern” ontology development is (a) there is standard documentation for editors to consult written in a standard form (b) this standard documentation is computable, which allows editors to see (i) which classes have logical definitions not conforming to any existing pattern (ii) where terminological usage varies or is inconsistent. Crucially the goal is **NOT** to force everything into a robotic form of consistency, this may be inappropriate for the domain, it is to allow the editor to understand this variation, to spot red flags and fill gaps, etc.

Workflow:

1. Create YAMLs (ideally first but this can be done retrospectively, after step 2)
2. Edit OWL in Protege as usual
3. Occasionally: run dosdp query to generate TSVs from YAML + OWL
 - a. Examine TSVs
 - b. Are there gaps, e.g. classes in ontology that don't conform
4. Release as usual

5. Continued maintenance: go to 2 (or occasionally 1)

Strengths:

- Preserves and improves standard ontology editing workflows
- The generated TSVs may serve other purposes
- This is a great methodology for reviewing existing logical definitions. Ontology engineers get served with a TSV with a list of terms supposedly in line with the abnormal morphology pattern - it is cognitively super easy to just skim through the labels and identify terms that are misplaced (i.e. do not belong in this pattern). We have done this extensively with HP, MP and WBPhenotype.

Weaknesses:

- Still need better tooling and reporting to really realize the strength of this approach

Examples:

- HP, MP (whole ontology)

Workflow 5: Augmentation

An ontology that is managed primarily through Protege is augmented with additional axioms based on DOSDP templates (for example auto-generated synonyms to help text miners; or fill in missing definitions). These can be vetted and incorporated back into the ontology. There is no TSV editing here, the axioms are generated via a parse-generate composition.

Workflow

1. Create YAMLs (ideally first but this can be done retrospectively, after step 2)
2. Edit OWL in Protege as usual
3. Occasionally: run candidate axiom generation
 - a. Dosdp query (OWL->TSV)
 - b. Dosdp generate (TSV->OWL)
 - i. Q: cross-product synonym - hints in the pattern? Dosdp tools the right place? Switch in DOSDPT only to say: use synonym field in synonyms, labels in exatSynonym, relatedSyn in syn.
 - c. Select axiom set of interest; e.g syns, names, text defs (robot filter)
 - d. **Manually examine axiom set, to include/exclude as required**
 - i. **Can we do all this in Protege (science fiction)**
 - ii. **Formally describe the process using OBO file review**
 - e. Merge back into main ontology (robot merge)
4. Release as normal
5. Continued editing as normal (step 2, occasionally step 1)

Strengths:

- As documentative
- Good for gap filling certain kinds of things that would be tedious (e.g. neoplasm synonyms based in Uberon synonyms in disease ontologies)

Weaknesses:

- A bit fiddly to set up and run the candidate axiom generation workflow

Examples:

- MONDO (see Mosscide video for example of workflow)

Use cases:

- Think auxiliary external files for text mining use cases.

Workflow 6: Gap filling

The goal here is to gap fill. For example, in GO if we have a 'negative regulation' term should we have a parent 'regulation' term? If we have 'cancer of X' should we have 'neoplasm of X'. From a strict logical perspective there is no need to add a named class unless there is a need to use (and even here a class expression could be used). However, ragged inconsistent lattices are problematic from a variety of perspectives.

See section on CL here

<https://douroucoulis.wordpress.com/2020/09/04/the-open-world-assumption-considered-harmful/>

The idea here is we have ways to fill in TSVs; this can be used in combination with other patterns (e.g. seed + augmentative)

Workflow 7: Autosuggestion of patterns and logical definitions

Outside the scope here, see the [patternizer draft](#)

The basic idea is to take an ontology without official DPs and use the patternizer to infer the YAMLS. This is a heuristic process.

Workflow 8: Integrated template and direct editing

Unfortunately, we do not have the tooling for this. Ideally, we would have people edit in either Protege or on the TSV. Protege would know that for example a removal of an axiom that is generated should be transacted as an edit on the TSV.

Workflow 9: AI based workflows

In the decade since DP-based workflows have been in development, Large Language Models have taken the center stage. These are good at generative tasks, including generating ontology terms. Tools such as DRAGON-AI⁷ leverage Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) to populate terms. Like with DOSDPs this seems to work well in cases where ontologies are compositional and information in orthogonal ontologies can inform terms. Rather than seeing these as competitive it makes more sense to figure out opportunities and complementariness - e.g can we generate and refine DPs using LLMs for maximal power? Also checking for disconnected between what is expected to belong to a pattern and what actually does may be a fruitful area. This may also benefit from viewing DPs as metaclasses, as in LinkML-OWL.

See also [Usage workflows for DOSDP templates](#)

Current usage in existing ontologies

Last updated: 2020-09-14

- Mondo
 - [Patterns](#)
 - Augmentation pattern historically used but abandoned due to difficulty to deploy
 - Documentation and Validation pattern in the making
- Phenotype ontologies
 - [uPheno](#)
 - Intermediate layer is completely template (TSV) driven, and the SSPOs are classified underneath. You could actually say that this is a kind of new workflow: existing patterns across SSPOs are matched, and based on the matches a layer of species independent classes are produced.
 - [PLANP](#) (purely TSV driven)
 - MP (documentation)
 - HP (documentation, partial skeleton (one-off generation of branches))
 - [FYPO](#) (augmentation, [switch pattern workflow](#))
 - [PHIPO](#) (augmentation - only generating EQ definitions)
 - WPO (augmentation - only generating EQ definitions)
 - [DPO](#) (augmentation - only generating EQ definitions)
 - [MGPO](#) (augmentation - only generating EQ definitions)
 - [XPO](#) (Purely DOSDP-template driven, [configurable](#) pipeline that generates XPO terms from XAO in demand)

- exclusion list instead of blacklist
- Environmental ontologies
 - ENVO
 - [patterns](#)
 - (Partial) skeleton pattern - some branches are maintained as modules which are imported into main and edited as TSV.
 - ECTO
 - [Purely TSV driven](#)
- [NCIT](#)
 - Bridges to CL and Uberon (very simple pattern)
 - Some more [complex patterns](#), but I can see them used anywhere (documentation workflow?) - documentation
- GO
 - under-used/not used
 - [Original set authored by David](#), focused on particular use cases
 - Jim picking it up?
 - went through all, fix all the syntax to run with dosdptools
 - regenerated tsvs
 - now its just logical fillers
- CL
 - DOSDPs not used, even for trivial cases like X cell part of A anatomy
 - Open [ticket](#)
 - Tending towards a mixed model of robot-style/DOSDP?
 - This will reinforce over-specification: <https://github.com/obophenotype/cell-ontology/issues/694>
- Anatomy
 - UBERON
 - Much work needs to be done
 - <https://github.com/obophenotype/uberont/issues/1184> -- from 2015
 - [PLANA](#)
 - [FBBT](#)
- OBA
 - [Purely TSV driven](#)
- [OBI](#)
 - Robot templates
- [MAXO](#)
 - Skeleton (partial) - some branches are maintained as modules which are imported into main and edited as TSV.
- Plant world
 - [PECO](#)
 - [PSO](#)
 - Previously named OOPS
 - Purely TSV-driven (amendment: not [purely](#))

- [AGRO](#)
- [PTO](#)
- [SRPDO](#)
- Application ontologies
 - [Cambridge Portal ontology](#)
 - [Simro](#)
 - [Phenoscape](#)
- Abandoned
 - [Expression patterns](#)

Other related workflows:

- **Pattern development**
 - Community based pattern review (reviewing, debating, signing)
 - Pattern validation through pattern.owl (Quo vadis?)
 - Patternizer -> suggest -> incorporate

Relevant tickets

- [Define design patterns using standard \(CL\)](#)
- Protege view table plugins. Inspiration:
 - cellfie plugin
 - matrix plugin

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